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FIRM-LEVEL CORRELATES OF LOW-CARBON INNOVATION IN CHINESE AGRIBUSINESS FIRMS

This study examines firm-level correlates of low-carbon innovation among Chinese agribusiness-related listed firms. Using a pooled firm-year panel of 316 firms and 3,920 observations from 1998 to 2021, it treats low-carbon patenting as a sparse innovation outcome rather than as a routinely observed continuous variable: 93.1% of firm-year observations record no low-carbon patent application. The empirical design separates two descriptive margins: whether a firm files at least one low-carbon patent in a given year and how the unconditional annual count varies across the full firm-year sample. The count outcome is estimated with pooled Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood, while the occurrence margin is examined with pooled linear probability, logit, and complementary log-log specifications. The explanatory variables are organized into resource-capability conditions, adjacent innovation stocks, and supplementary linkage proxies. Across specifications, firm size and selected balance-sheet structure variables are the most stable correlates of low-carbon patenting. Pre-period green patent stock is the strongest adjacent innovation correlate. Because green and low-carbon patent categories may overlap, the study uses exact patent-level overlap exclusion as the main measurement check, and the positive green-stock association remains. Pre-period digital patent stock is more sensitive to model design and is more visible in occurrence and onset evidence than in full-sample count models. Branch-based geographic-reach proxies and static equity-link proxies add only limited incremental explanatory value after firm characteristics and lagged innovation stocks are controlled for. The findings are descriptive rather than causal and mainly reflect between-firm differences in the pooled panel. They suggest that low-carbon patenting in this sector is concentrated among larger and more innovation-capable firms rather than being a general outcome of network expansion.

Key words: *agribusiness-related listed firms; low-carbon innovation; green patents; digital patents; sparse outcomes; PPML; China.*

Introduction. Low-carbon innovation is related to but narrower than broader green innovation. Environmental innovation is shaped jointly by regulation, technological opportunity, market incentives, and firm heterogeneity rather than by a single determinant (Jaffe & Palmer, 1997; Porter & van der Linde, 1995). Eco-innovation studies also show that environmentally oriented innovation varies across sectors, firms, and institutional settings (Horbach, 2008; Rennings, 2000). In Chinese listed firms, recent studies examine low-carbon innovation under low-carbon city pilots, digital-economy policy, and pilot free trade zones (Pan et al., 2022; Yu et al., 2023; Luo et al., 2024; Hunjra et al., 2024; Pan & Cao, 2024). Yet agriculture-related listed firms remain less directly studied, and the closest evidence still focuses more on green transformation than on low-carbon patenting itself (Yuan et al., 2024). This paper therefore asks which firm characteristics are observed alongside low-carbon patenting in agribusiness-related listed firms and whether those patterns differ between annual occurrence and unconditional annual count outcomes.

A distributional issue is central to this setting. At the firm-year level, low-carbon

patenting is not simply a smaller version of ordinary innovation activity; it is a rare event with a dominant mass at zero. Consequently, the factors associated with crossing the annual occurrence threshold may differ from the factors associated with the unconditional annual count in the full sample. The paper therefore avoids treating the dependent variable as a conventional continuous outcome and instead uses count and occurrence models as complementary descriptive views of the same sparse innovation process. Low-carbon innovation in agribusiness-related listed firms is also worth examining because these firms occupy an intermediate position between primary agriculture, food processing, biological resources, agricultural inputs, logistics, and downstream consumption. Their innovation activities are not identical to those of heavy industrial emitters, but they are still connected to energy use, production efficiency, resource recycling, packaging, cold-chain logistics, and environmentally oriented product development. This makes the sector suitable for studying low-carbon innovation as a firm-level capability, while also requiring caution in interpretation. A listed agribusiness-related firm may file low-carbon patents because it has accumulated technical knowledge, because it faces external environmental expectations, or because it has broader organizational resources that support patenting in general. The empirical design therefore focuses on conditional correlates rather than on a single deterministic explanation.

The argument is organized around three explanatory layers. First, the resource-based view, natural-resource-based view, and absorptive-capacity theory imply that low-carbon innovation depends on scale, slack, prior knowledge, and organizational capacity (Barney, 1991; Hart, 1995; Hart & Dowell, 2011; Cohen & Levinthal, 1990). Related evidence links governance, ownership, financial development, and environmental regulation to green or environmental innovation (Amore & Bennesen, 2016; K. Wang & Jiang, 2021; Kong et al., 2024). Second, adjacent innovation capability may matter. Green innovation is close to low-carbon innovation but not identical to it, and accumulated green patents may proxy related routines and knowledge stocks (Brunnermeier & Cohen, 2003; D. Zhang et al., 2019). Digital capability may support information processing, internal control, financing access, and innovation coordination, and recent studies associate digital transformation or digital finance with green or low-carbon innovation (X. Li et al., 2022; M. Tang et al., 2023; Zheng & Zhang, 2023; Xu et al., 2024; H. Li et al., 2024; Lyu et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2024; J. Zhang et al., 2025). Third, external organizational linkages may affect information access and monitoring, as suggested by network, supply-chain, investor, and site-visit evidence (Ahuja, 2000; Jiang & Bai, 2022; L. Wang et al., 2023; X. Zhang et al., 2023; He & Shen, 2024; Jin et al., 2024; H. Tang et al., 2024). These linkages are treated here as supplementary proxies rather than as a comprehensive network-embeddedness measure.

The paper contributes by aligning model choice with the sparse distribution of low-carbon patents, by comparing resource-capability conditions, adjacent innovation stocks, and linkage proxies within a common pooled framework, and by testing whether the green-stock association survives exact patent-level overlap exclusion. The hypotheses and research questions are deliberately descriptive: H1a predicts a positive association between firm size and both low-carbon occurrence and count outcomes; H1b expects selected balance-sheet ratios to be associated with low-carbon innovation without imposing strong sign restrictions; H2 expects pre-period green patent stock to remain positively associated after exact overlap exclusion; RQ1 asks whether pre-period digital stock is more visible on the occurrence margin than in the full-sample count model; and RQ2 asks whether the branch and equity-link proxies add information beyond firm characteristics and lagged innovation stocks.

Materials and methods. The analytical panel is built from agribusiness-related listed firms identified in the Qiyang Big Data Platform for Social Sciences. Annual financial statements define the firm-year backbone, after which patent-based innovation measures and auxiliary linkage objects are merged. Firm identifiers are harmonized across source tables, duplicate firm-

patent-year observations are removed before aggregation, and firms are retained regardless of whether they ever file a low-carbon patent. This construction rule is important because excluding never-innovating firms would mechanically weaken the sparse-event structure and would shift the analysis toward already innovative firms. The core pooled sample contains 316 firms and 3,920 firm-year observations from 1998 to 2021.

Low-carbon, green, and digital patent measures follow the original database labels rather than a new manual reclassification. Low-carbon and green patents are mapped through the corporate patent-applicant identifier, while digital patents are mapped through the legal-person patent-right identifier. Patent applications are aggregated by application year, and granted low-carbon patents are aggregated by grant year. When application numbers are missing, patent numbers are used to construct the patent key; observations are then de-duplicated at the firm-patent-year level before annual aggregation. This procedure reduces repeated counting of the same patent record but does not eliminate all possible measurement noise in database labels or firm-name matching.

The main outcome is the annual count of low-carbon patent applications, denoted LCI_{it} , where i indexes firms and t indexes years. The occurrence outcome is defined as

$$HasLCI_{it} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if firm } i \text{ files at least one low-carbon patent in year } t, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Stricter robustness outcomes are the annual counts of low-carbon invention patents and granted low-carbon patents, which test whether the empirical ordering survives under more demanding patent definitions.

The regressors are grouped into three blocks. R_{it} contains resource-capability variables: $\ln(Assets_{it})$, leverage, return on assets, operating cash flow over assets, cash over assets, and fixed assets over assets. S_{it} contains pre-period adjacent innovation stocks:

$$GreenStock_{i,t-1} = \ln(1 + \text{cumulative green patents of firm } i \text{ up to year } t - 1), \quad (2)$$

$$DigitalStock_{i,t-1} = \ln(1 + \text{cumulative digital patents of firm } i \text{ up to year } t - 1). \quad (3)$$

N_{it} contains linkage proxies: $\ln(1 + \text{outside branches}_{it})$, outside branch share, $\ln(1 + \text{branch provinces}_{it})$, outside investee share, $\ln(1 + \text{investees}_i)$, and mean equity share. Branch variables are contemporaneous, investment-link variables are static firm-level measures, and innovation stocks are lagged cumulative measures; therefore, coefficients are compared as conditional associations, not as causal effects. Because the green and low-carbon patent categories may overlap, the retained measurement check removes green patents that share the exact patent key with low-carbon patents before re-aggregating adjusted green patents to the firm-year level. This check is not intended to prove that green and low-carbon innovation are completely separate technological domains. Rather, it asks a narrower measurement question: whether the positive green-stock association is driven only by patents that are simultaneously classified as low-carbon. If the association remains after exact patent-key exclusion, the result is more consistent with adjacent technological relatedness than with a purely mechanical overlap between patent categories. The interpretation remains conservative, because firms with stronger green patent histories may also have stronger general patenting propensity, better innovation management, or higher attention to environmental topics.

The main count model is a pooled Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood specification:

$$\mathbb{E}(LCI_{it} | X_{it}) = \exp(\alpha + R'_{it}\beta_R + S'_{it}\beta_S + N'_{it}\beta_N + O'_{it}\beta_O + \lambda_t + \mu_j), \quad (4)$$

where O_{it} denotes ownership-group controls;
 λ_t denotes year fixed effects;
 μ_j denotes industry fixed effects.
 X_{it} represents the full set of included regressors and controls.
 The occurrence margin is first estimated using a pooled linear probability model:

$$\mathbb{E}(HasLCI_{it} | X_{it}) = \alpha + R'_{it}\beta_R + S'_{it}\beta_S + N'_{it}\beta_N + O'_{it}\beta_O + \lambda_t + \mu_j. \quad (5)$$

It is also estimated using a pooled logit model:

$$\Pr(HasLCI_{it} = 1 | X_{it}) = \Lambda(\alpha + R'_{it}\beta_R + S'_{it}\beta_S + N'_{it}\beta_N + O'_{it}\beta_O + \lambda_t + \mu_j), \quad (6)$$

where $\Lambda(\cdot)$ is the logistic cumulative distribution function.

Standard errors are clustered at the firm level. Supplementary checks include complementary log-log models, stricter-outcome PPML models, sample and time-stability checks, lagged firm fixed-effects models, and an onset logit model. PPML follows the logic of estimating non-negative outcomes with many zeros under heteroskedasticity (Silva & Tenreyro, 2006), while the binary-response models follow standard generalized linear model practice (McCullagh, 1989). AIC values are used only for relative fit comparisons within the same estimator and are not compared across PPML and logit models.

Results. Table 1 confirms the sparse-outcome setting. The mean annual low-carbon patent count is 0.154, and 93.1% of firm-year observations have zero low-carbon patent applications. The zero shares are even higher for low-carbon invention patents and granted patents. This pattern indicates that low-carbon patenting is not a routinely observed firm-year activity in the sample, but an infrequent outcome concentrated in a relatively small subset of observations.

Table 1. Sample structure and selected descriptive statistics

Item	Value	Item	Value
Sample period	1998-2021	Firms	316
Firm-year observations	3,920	Firms ever filing LC patents	92
Zero share: LC patent count	93.1%	Zero share: LC invention count	95.0%
Zero share: LC granted count	95.2%	Non-missing R&D/Revenue	27.8%
Mean LC patent count	0.154	Mean LC entry	0.069
Mean ln(Assets)	21.702	Mean Cash/Assets	0.179
Mean FA/Assets	0.277	Mean R&D/Revenue	0.021
Mean green stock (t-1)	0.597	Mean digital stock (t-1)	0.129

Note: LC denotes low-carbon. Green and digital stocks are pre-period cumulative patent stocks transformed as $\ln(1 + \text{cumulative patents up to } t-1)$.

Source: authors' calculations based on Qiyang Big Data Platform for Social Sciences and firms' annual financial statements.

Figure 1 describes the time evolution of low-carbon innovation. Both the annual occurrence rate and the mean annual patent count increase over the sample period, especially after the late 2000s. However, the levels remain low in absolute terms, indicating that the upward trend does not remove the sparse-event nature of the outcome. The figure therefore supports the

decision to distinguish between the occurrence margin and the unconditional count margin.

Fig 1. Low-carbon innovation over time

Note: The solid line reports the annual occurrence rate, and the dashed line reports the mean annual low-carbon patent count.

Source: authors' calculations based on Qiyan Big Data Platform for Social Sciences and firms' annual financial statements.

Figure 2 further clarifies the distributional shape of the dependent variable. The firm-year distribution is dominated by zero observations, while positive patent counts are relatively rare and high-count observations are rarer still. This distributional feature justifies the use of PPML for count outcomes and separate binary-response models for annual occurrence, rather than treating low-carbon patenting as a conventional continuous outcome.

Fig 2. Distribution of low-carbon patent counts

Note: The histogram reports the firm-year distribution of annual low-carbon patent applications.

Source: authors' calculations based on Qiyan Big Data Platform for Social Sciences and firms' annual financial statements.

Table 1 also shows why R&D intensity cannot serve as a stable baseline control in this dataset: the non-missing share of R&D/Revenue is only 27.8%. Therefore the baseline estimates should be interpreted as reduced-form firm-level correlates rather than as coefficients fully net of direct R&D-input differences. The descriptive statistics further show that pre-period green stock is more common than pre-period digital stock, which is relevant when interpreting the stronger and more stable green-stock coefficient. This descriptive pattern also supports the decision to separate the count and occurrence margins. When the outcome contains many zeros, a positive coefficient in the count model reflects changes in the unconditional expected number of patents in the full firm-year population, not only changes among firms that already file low-carbon patents. By contrast, the occurrence model is closer to the question of whether a firm crosses the annual entry threshold into low-carbon patenting. These two estimands are related but not equivalent. A variable may be associated with the probability of observing any low-carbon patent while having a weaker association with the unconditional annual number of patents. This distinction is especially relevant for interpreting the digital-stock result.

Table 2 reports the pooled PPML count estimates. Adding adjacent innovation stocks reduces the AIC from 3203 to 2943, while adding the linkage-proxy block reduces it further to 2894. Within the network-extended model, $\ln(\text{Assets})$ remains positive and significant (0.361, $p < 0.01$). Cash/Assets and FA/Assets are also positive and significant, while OCF/Assets is negative. These balance-sheet coefficients should not be interpreted as independent causal mechanisms because the ratios are mechanically related and measured contemporaneously. Green stock (t-1) is positive and highly significant (0.542, $p < 0.01$), whereas Digital stock (t-1) is not retained after linkage proxies are added. The linkage proxies are weaker: only Outside branch share is marginally positive, while the remaining branch and equity-link variables are not statistically stable. Thus, the count evidence places the main explanatory weight on firm size, selected balance-sheet structure, and adjacent green innovation stock.

Table 2. Baseline count results: PPML estimates

Variable	Resource	+ adjacent stocks	+ linkage proxies
$\ln(\text{Assets})$	0.607*** (0.091)	0.470*** (0.110)	0.361*** (0.123)
OCF/Assets	-2.340* (1.422)	-3.979*** (1.356)	-3.945*** (1.249)
Cash/Assets	2.621** (1.093)	2.823** (1.119)	3.040*** (0.955)
FA/Assets	1.905** (0.770)	2.497*** (0.722)	3.001*** (0.672)
Green stock (t-1)	—	0.580*** (0.086)	0.542*** (0.089)
Digital stock (t-1)	—	0.074 (0.104)	-0.012 (0.122)
Outside branch share	—	—	0.731* (0.373)
$\ln(1+\text{Outside branches})$	—	—	-0.379 (0.305)
$\ln(1+\text{Branch provinces})$	—	—	0.476 (0.405)
Outside investee share	—	—	0.833 (0.510)
$\ln(1+\text{Investees})$	—	—	0.217 (0.172)
Mean equity share	—	—	0.270 (0.953)
AIC	3203.290	2943.230	2894.023

Note: All models include year fixed effects, industry fixed effects, and ownership-group controls. Firm-clustered standard errors are in parentheses. ***, **, and * denote significance at the 1%, 5%, and 10% levels.

Source: authors' calculations based on Qiyang Big Data Platform for Social Sciences and firms' annual financial statements.

Table 3 shows the occurrence-model evidence. The logit AIC declines from 1674 in the resource-only model to 1602 after adjacent innovation stocks are added, and then only slightly to 1598 after linkage proxies enter. Firm size, FA/Assets, Green stock (t-1), and Digital stock (t-1) are positive in the adjacent-innovation logit model. Digital stock is therefore more visible on the occurrence margin than in the full-sample PPML count model. This pattern supports RQ1 in a qualified descriptive sense: digital capability appears more related to entering low-carbon patenting than to generating larger unconditional annual counts.

Table 3. Occurrence-model results: logit estimates

Variable	Resource	+ adjacent stocks	+ linkage proxies
ln(Assets)	0.785*** (0.096)	0.669*** (0.101)	0.633*** (0.119)
Lev	-1.219* (0.650)	-1.202* (0.627)	-1.048 (0.642)
OCF/Assets	-1.612 (1.199)	-2.717** (1.213)	-2.631** (1.203)
Cash/Assets	1.275 (0.785)	1.212 (0.830)	1.169 (0.809)
FA/Assets	1.906** (0.793)	1.781** (0.739)	1.812** (0.714)
Green stock (t-1)	—	0.480*** (0.095)	0.462*** (0.103)
Digital stock (t-1)	—	0.256** (0.130)	0.181 (0.136)
Outside branch share	—	—	0.140 (0.428)
ln(1+Branch provinces)	—	—	-0.080 (0.380)
Outside investee share	—	—	0.829 (0.508)
AIC	1674.172	1602.250	1597.637

Note: The dependent variable equals one when the firm files at least one low-carbon patent in a given year. Controls and standard-error conventions follow Table 2.

Source: authors' calculations based on Qiyan Big Data Platform for Social Sciences and firms' annual financial statements.

Table 4 summarizes the retained robustness evidence. Exact patent-level overlap exclusion preserves the positive green-stock association in both logit and PPML models, supporting H2 as adjacent innovation relatedness rather than as a clean complementarity mechanism. Stricter outcomes also preserve the main ordering: green stock remains positive for low-carbon invention and granted patent counts, while digital stock is not robustly retained in these PPML models. Lagged firm fixed-effects PPML models do not retain the focal count coefficients, indicating that the pooled count results mainly reflect between-firm heterogeneity. By contrast, the lagged LPM and onset logit results are more consistent with occurrence and first-entry interpretations. The time-split evidence also suggests that the green-stock association is clearer in the later period, so the pooled narrative should not be read as a time-invariant relationship.

Overall, H1a is supported: firm size is positive across the main count and occurrence specifications. H1b is supported only descriptively: selected balance-sheet ratios matter, but their signs and stability differ across margins and should not be over-theorized. H2 is supported in a qualified sense after exact overlap exclusion. RQ2 receives a conservative answer: the specific branch-based geographic-reach proxies and static equity-link proxies used here add limited incremental explanatory value once firm characteristics and pre-period innovation stocks are included.

Table 4. Retained robustness evidence

Check	Outcome/model	Selected retained evidence	Interpretation
Exact overlap exclusion	Logit, LC entry	$\ln(\text{Assets})=0.695^{***}$; Exact adj. green stock= 0.384^{***} ; Digital stock= 0.276^{**}	Green-stock result survives patent-level exclusion.
Exact overlap exclusion	PPML, LC count	$\ln(\text{Assets})=0.499^{***}$; Cash/Assets= 2.816^{**} ; FA/Assets= 2.464^{***} ; Exact adj. green stock= 0.489^{***} ; Digital stock= 0.086	Green stock remains robust; digital stock is not retained in the count model.
Stricter outcomes	PPML, invention/granted counts	Green stock remains positive for both outcomes; digital stock is not robustly significant.	Main ordering survives stricter patent definitions.
Lagged firm FE	PPML, LC count	Focal coefficients are not statistically retained.	Pooled count pattern mainly reflects between-firm heterogeneity.
Lagged LPM / onset	LC entry / first entry	Green stock is retained in lagged LPM; digital stock is retained in onset logit.	Occurrence and entry evidence differ from full-sample count evidence.

Note: Exact overlap exclusion removes green patents sharing the exact patent key with low-carbon patents before re-aggregation. Lagged firm fixed-effects and onset models are used only as supplementary evidence.

Source: authors' calculations based on Qiyang Big Data Platform for Social Sciences and firms' annual financial statements.

Discussion. The results suggest that low-carbon patenting in agribusiness-related listed firms is more commonly observed among larger firms with selected balance-sheet capacity and stronger adjacent green innovation accumulation. This is consistent with resource-capability and absorptive-capacity arguments (Barney, 1991; Cohen & Levinthal, 1990; Hart, 1995), but the evidence is descriptive. Because the main specifications are pooled rather than causal designs, they mainly compare firms with different characteristics instead of identifying within-firm responses to exogenous shocks.

Green stock is the most stable adjacent innovation correlate. However, even after exact overlap exclusion, the result should be read as adjacent relatedness rather than as a clean mechanism. Firms with accumulated green patents may have related technological routines, but they may also have broader patenting propensity, managerial attention to environmental topics, or unobserved innovation orientation. The empirical design cannot fully separate these explanations.

The digital-stock evidence is weaker and margin-specific. It is clearer in occurrence and onset evidence than in unconditional count models, which fits the idea that digital capability may help firms cross the entry threshold into low-carbon patenting but does not necessarily predict larger annual counts once the full mass of zeros is retained. Therefore the manuscript should not claim that digital innovation is a dominant driver. The linkage-proxy evidence is also narrow: the

branch and equity-link measures capture geographic reach and static ownership links, not the full structure of interorganizational networks. The limited role of the linkage-proxy block should therefore not be interpreted as evidence that networks are unimportant. It only indicates that the particular proxies available here do not add much stable explanatory information after firm characteristics and lagged innovation stocks are included. More refined network measures, such as supply-chain centrality, repeated R&D collaboration, patent co-application networks, director interlocks, or dynamic investor networks, may capture different mechanisms. The current evidence is consequently best read as a negative or weak result for branch-based geographic reach and static equity links, not for network embeddedness as a broader theoretical construct.

Several boundaries follow from this design. First, the study uses patent outputs, not unobserved innovation effort or commercialization success; the results therefore speak to observed patenting rather than to realized emission reduction. Second, the pooled models control for observable firm characteristics, industry, ownership group, and year effects, but they do not use exogenous treatment variation. Third, the network variables are only available proxies and should not be generalized to all possible network mechanisms. These boundaries are not defects to be hidden; they define the proper evidentiary status of the manuscript.

Conclusion. This study examines firm-level correlates of low-carbon innovation in Chinese agribusiness-related listed firms from 1998 to 2021. The evidence shows that low-carbon patenting is sparse, with 93.1% zero firm-year observations. Across pooled PPML, logit, and supplementary checks, firm size, selected balance-sheet variables, and pre-period green innovation stock are the most stable correlates. Digital stock is more design-sensitive and appears more clearly in occurrence and onset evidence than in the unconditional count model. The branch-based and equity-link proxies used here add only limited incremental information. These findings also clarify the empirical ranking of the explanatory blocks. Resource-capability conditions and accumulated green innovation provide the most stable descriptive signals. Digital innovation is not irrelevant, but its association is concentrated more on the occurrence and onset margins than on the unconditional count outcome. The linkage proxies are the weakest block in the present measurement setting. This ranking is useful because it prevents the paper from overstating fashionable but less stable explanations. In this sample, low-carbon patenting appears less like a general consequence of network expansion and more like an uneven innovation outcome concentrated among larger and more innovation-capable firms.

The implications are therefore limited. The results suggest that low-carbon patenting is concentrated among firms with greater scale, selected resource capacity, and related innovation accumulation, but they do not identify policy effects, managerial treatment effects, or causal channels. For managers, the evidence points to the importance of building cumulative green innovation capability before expecting low-carbon patenting to become routine. For policy discussion, the evidence is more useful for screening firm heterogeneity than for evaluating the effect of any single intervention. Future work should use stronger identification designs, richer direct measures of R&D input and organizational networks, and more detailed patent-quality measures. It should also examine whether the observed relationships differ across policy regimes, ownership groups, and subsectors within agribusiness.

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КОРРЕЛЯЦИИ НИЗКОУГЛЕРОДНЫХ ИННОВАЦИЙ НА УРОВНЕ КОМПАНИЙ В КИТАЙСКИХ АГРОФИРМАХ

В данном исследовании рассматриваются корреляции низкоуглеродных инноваций на уровне фирм среди китайских компаний агробизнеса, зарегистрированных на бирже. Используя объединенную панель данных за год из 316 фирм и 3920 наблюдений за период с 1998 по 2021 год, рассматривается патентование низкоуглеродных технологий как редкий инновационный результат, а не как регулярно наблюдаемая непрерывная переменная: в 93,1% наблюдений за год, проведенных фирмами, не зафиксировано ни одной заявки на низкоуглеродный патент. Эмпирический анализ позволяет разделить два показателя: подает ли фирма хотя бы один патент на низкоуглеродную продукцию в течение определенного года и как меняется безусловный годовой показатель по всей выборке за год работы фирмы. Результат подсчета оценивается с помощью объединенной пуассоновской псевдомаксимальной вероятности, в то время как предел вероятности возникновения оценивается с помощью объединенной линейной вероятности, логит-коэффициента и дополнительных логарифмических спецификаций. Независимые переменные сгруппированы по условиям ресурсных возможностей, смежным запасам инноваций и дополнительным показателям взаимосвязи. С точки зрения технических требований, размер фирмы и выбранные переменные структуры баланса являются наиболее стабильными показателями, влияющими на патентование низкоуглеродных технологий. Запас патентов на «зеленые» технологии, накопленный до истечения срока действия, является наиболее сильным показателем, связанным с инновациями. Поскольку категории патентов «зеленый» и «низкоуглеродистый» могут пересекаться, в исследовании в качестве основного критерия измерения используется точное исключение совпадений на уровне патентов, и сохраняется положительная связь между «зеленым» и «низкоуглеродистым» запасами. Запас цифровых патентов, выданных до начала периода, более чувствителен к дизайну модели и более заметен в свидетельствах о появлении и сроках действия, чем в моделях с полным подсчетом выборок. Прокси с географическим охватом на основе филиалов и статические прокси с привязкой к акционерному капиталу дают лишь ограниченную дополнительную объяснительную ценность после проверки характеристик фирмы и запаздывающих инновационных запасов. Полученные результаты носят скорее описательный, а не причинно-следственный характер, и в основном отражают различия между фирмами в объединенной группе. Они предполагают, что патентование низкоуглеродных технологий в этом секторе сосредоточено среди более крупных и способных к инновациям фирм, а не является общим результатом расширения сети.

***Ключевые слова:** листинговые компании агробизнеса; низкоуглеродные инновации; «зеленые» патенты; цифровые патенты; редкие результаты; PPML; Китай.*

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